

New data on the ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae) from Kosovo

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Abstract: New records of ground beetle collected from 29 localities in Kosovo are presented. Collection of the material was carried out in the period 2018–2019. Altogether, 69 species and subspecies of ground beetles are identified. Twenty one species and four genera are recorded for the first time for the fauna of Kosovo. In addition, five species and two genera are first reported from Kosovo with first detailed records. Importance of premeditated efforts for collecting material in less investigated areas in the Western Balkans is also evidenced by finding of a great total of species that represent second records for Kosovo.

Keywords: Balkan Peninsula, Carabidae, new records

Introduction

The ground beetle fauna of the Balkan Peninsula numbers 1632 species (B. Guéorguiev, unpublished data). Relatively well investigated and catalogued are the faunas in the central, east and south part of the Peninsula, namely those of Bulgaria (Hieke & Wrase, 1988; Guéorguiev & Guéorguiev, 1995), Serbia (Ćurčić et al., 2007), Albania (Guéorguiev, 2007), Greece (Arndt et al., 2011), North Macedonia (Hristovski & Guéorguiev, 2015) and European Turkey (Kostova & Guéorguiev, 2016). In spite of the fauna of the Western Balkans (Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Kosovo) is catalogued and with taxonomic composition well-known (Löbl & Löbl, 2017), particular areas in the region remain less investigated than others mostly for the lack of reliable fresh data.

First information about carabids from the region of Kosovo was provided by Apfelbeck (1904) who enlisted 43 species from environs of Prizren, considering the current nomenclature of the Palaearctic representatives of the family (Löbl & Löbl, 2017). The Hungarian Ernő Csiki (Csiki, 1940) is that who so far made the most important contribution to the fauna of Kosovo.

This author gave data for 105 species and two subspecies from the region. In the beginning of the XXI century all the available information on the carabids from Kosovo has been summarised in the work of Ćurčić et al. (2007), which is a sound basis for further research of the regional fauna. Not long ago, Guéorguiev (2011) added first data for 14 species and subspecies ground beetles for the area investigated.

In consequence of deliberate efforts for collecting new information for projects on the species for Red List for Kosovo and endemic terrestrial plants and animals in the Western Balkans, new data about ground beetles from Kosovo were collected in the years of 2018 and 2019. Thus, the aim of the present report is to present the result of the identifications of the collected samples and to make them public.

Materials and methods

The material of ground beetles was collected by hand and pitfall traps with vinegar in the period 2018–2019 at the following habitats: forests, alpine and subalpine pastures and meadows, open places, habitats at riverbanks and around streams as well as semi-natural

Fig. 1. Map of and Kosovo with indications of the localities from which the material was collected [abbreviations of localities are presented in Materials and methods section; scale bar = 13 km].

and ruderal habitats in suburban areas. Most samples were collected at altitudes between 1000 and 2500 m a.s.l. at western and southern border of Kosovo on mountains of huge massifs of Bjeshket e nemuna/Prokletije and Malet e Sharrit/Šar Planina, with the exception of lowland localities in central Kosovo near the villages and towns of Dečan/Dečani, Ponorc/Ponorac, Kabash i Hasit/Kabaš Has, Ponorc/Ponorac and Nerodime e Epërme/Gornje Nerodimlje (Fig. 1).

The whole material was collected by the second author and is currently kept in his private collection. The following list presents the sampled sites with habitats and sampling dates, and their abbreviations used further in the text.

List of localities

- K01 Kosovo SE, Shtërpcë/Štrpce Municipality, Piribeg, 2200–2400 m a.s.l., 21.09.2018, subalpine meadows, (42.180015° 21.055152°).
- K02 Kosovo SE, Shtërpcë/Štrpce Municipality, Suva Reka River, Prevala/Prevalac, 1200 m a.s.l., 21.09–4.10.2018, pitfall traps, beech forest, (42.182433° 20.978054°).
- K03 Kosovo W, Desan/Dečani Municipality, Mali i Strelcit/Streočka Planina, Streočki Stanovi, 1850 m, 2.10.2018, subalpine meadows, (42.5865° 20.237°).

- K04 Kosovo W, Peja/Peć Municipality, Hajla Mt above Koshutan/Košutane, 1900 m a.s.l., 1.10.2018, subalpine meadows, (42.764715° 20.102792°).
- K05 Kosovo W, Peja/Peć Municipality, Kuqishtë/Kučište, 2.5 km N to Bogë/Boge, 1150 m a.s.l., 18.09–1.10.2018, pitfall traps, mixed deciduous – coniferous forest, (42.7073° 20.0609°).
- K06 Kosovo W, Desan/Dečani Municipality, Lumbardhi i Deçanit/Dečanska Bistrica River, 4.5 km NW from Dečan/Dečani, 800 m a.s.l., 19.09.2018, deciduous forest with dense shrubs, (42.557656° 20.235988°).
- K07 Kosovo S, Dragash/Dragaš Municipality, Brod, Zlipotocka Planina/Zlipotočka Planina, 1600–1800 m a.s.l., 20.09.2018, subalpine and alpine pastures, (41.9554° 20.709°).
- K08 Kosovo SC, Kačanik/Kaçanik Municipality, Vataj/Vata, Bujevo, 1050 m a.s.l., 5.10.2018, beech forest, (42.2207° 21.1907°).
- K09 Kosovo SE, Prizren Municipality, Prevala/Prevalac, Suva Reka River, 1500 m a.s.l., 21.09.2018, ruderal vegetation by the road, (42.1807541° 20.953594°).
- K10 Kosovo W, Peja/Peć Municipality, Hajla Mt, ridge, 2340 m a.s.l., 13.07.2019, alpine pasture, (42.7547326° 20.1457226°).
- K11 Kosovo W, Peja/Peć Municipality, Adžovića Reka Stream, upper flow, 1250 m a.s.l., 19.09.2018, riparian habitats at the stream banks, (42.708888° 20.041677°).
- K12 Kosovo SC, Ferizaj/Uroševac Municipality, Golema Reka Stream, upper flow, 1250 m a.s.l., 4.10.2018, mesophilic habitats at the stream banks in the deciduous forest zone, (42.347248° 21.018802°).
- K13 Kosovo SC, Ferizaj/Uroševac Municipality, Jezerc/Jezerce, Kodra e Dlinjave Hill, 1200 m a.s.l., 4.10.2018, mesophilic meadow in the deciduous forests zone, (42.370685° 20.984815°).
- K14 Kosovo C, Malishevë/Mališevo Municipality, Ponorc/Ponorac, Accumulation Lake, 570 m a.s.l., 30.10.2018, habitats around the spring, (42.4882297° 20.6215972°).
- K15 Kosovo C, Malishevë/Mališevo Municipality, 2 km W from Ponorc/Ponorac, 760 m a.s.l., 30.10.2018, xeric habitat with ruderal vegetation, (42.5014° 20.6004°).
- K16 Kosovo SW, Prizren Municipality, Kabash i Hasit/Kabaš Has, Gurra Kabashit Spring, 340 m a.s.l., 3.10.2018, riparian habitats around the spring, (42.2709° 20.5525°).
- K17 Kosovo SW, Prizren Municipality, Duvška Gorge, 530 m a.s.l., 20.09.2018, xeric ruderal habitat by the road, (42.1939° 20.7753°).
- K18 Kosovo SC, Ferizaj/Uroševac Municipality, Nerodime e Epërme/Gornje Nerodimlje, hotel Villa, 670 m a.s.l., 4.10.2018, riparian habitats around the spring, (42.36632° 21.057824°).
- K19 Kosovo SW, Prizren Municipality, Poslishtë/Poslište, 340 m a.s.l., 4.10.2018, habitats at the stream bank, (42.1781° 20.6691°).
- K20 Kosovo C, Klina Municipality, Mirusha/Miruša Canyon, 370 m a.s.l., 30.09.2018, riparian habitats at the stream banks, (42.5237032° 20.5820268°).
- K21 Kosovo W, Desan/Dečani Municipality, Lumbardhi i Deçanit/Dečanska Bistrica river, 4,5 km NW Dečani, 800 m, 19.09–2.10.2018, pitfall traps, xeric mixed deciduous forest, (42.5573° 20.2384°).
- K22 Kosovo SE, Prizren Municipality, slopes of Popovo Prase Mt, Prevala/Prevalac, 1500 m a.s.l., 20.09.2018, beech forest, (42.1807541° 20.953594°).
- K23 Kosovo W, Gjakova/Đakovica Municipality, Gërçinë/Grčina, slopes of Paštrik Mt, 600 m a.s.l., 3.10.2018, xeric habitats in and around drained river bed surrounded by degraded deciduous forest, (42.289684° 20.475725°).
- K24 Kosovo SW, Prizren Municipality, Kabash i Hasit/Kabaš Has, Gurra Kabashit spring, 320 m a.s.l., 3.10.2018, riparian habitats around the spring, (42.2705° 20.5492°).
- K25 Kosovo SC, Gjakova/Đakovica municipality, Damjan/Damjane, spring near Villa Kroni, 350 m a.s.l., 3.10.2018, riparian habitats around the spring, (42.2873° 20.5136°).
- K26 Kosovo W, Peja/Peć Municipality, Bogë/Boge, 1350 m a.s.l., 18.09.2018, subalpine meadow on the site of cleared coniferous forest, (42.739871° 20.055401°).
- K27 Kosovo SW, Dragash/Dragaš Municipality, Brod, hotel Arxena, 1500 m a.s.l., 20.09.2018, subalpine meadows, (41.964508° 20.711909°).
- K28 Kosovo SW, Peja/Peć Municipality, Gryka e Rugovës/Rugovska Klisura Gorge, former

border crossing to Montenegro, 1200 m a.s.l., 1.10.2018, beech forest, (42.685286° 20.054004°).

K29 Kosovo W, Peja/Peć Municipality, Žljeb Mt., Peć – Rožaje road, 1450 m a.s.l., 18.09.2018, mesophilic riparian habitats at the stream banks, (42.778210° 20.268966°).

The following abbreviations are also used: ** – new taxon for the fauna of Kosovo; * – first detailed record(s) for the fauna of Kosovo; ex – individual(s). The map was generated through the online tool SimpleMappr (Shorthouse, 2010).

Results and discussion

In total 246 adult specimens belonging to 69 ground beetle species from 25 genera were collected and determined. The richest in terms of species are the genera *Harpalus* (10 species), *Bembidion* (9), *Trechus* (7), *Carabus* (6), *Calathus* (5) and *Pterostichus* (5). Coming next is an alphabetical list of species and subspecies of the ground beetles, the abbreviations of localities, from which they were caught, and number and/or sex of specimens.

Agonum (Agonum) muelleri (Herbst, 1784) – K07 (1 ♂).

**Amara (Bradytus) apricaria* (Paykull, 1790) – K07 (5 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀).

***Amara (Celia) bifrons* (Gyllenhal, 1810) – K07 (1 ♀).

Anchomenus dorsalis dorsalis Pontoppidan, 1763 – K04 (1 ♂); K07 (1 ♀); K12 (1 ♂); K13 (1 ♀).

Aptinus merditanus merditanus Apfelbeck, 1918 – K02 (1 ♀).

Bembidion (Bembidionetolitzkya) geniculatum geniculatum Heer, 1837 – K12 (3 ♂♂, 1 ♀).

Bembidion (Bembidionetolitzkya) tibiale (Duftschmid, 1812) – K05 (1 ♂); K11 (1 ♂, 1 ♀).

Bembidion (Metallina) lampros (Herbst, 1784) – K07 (2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀).

Bembidion (Ocydromus) decorum decorum (Panzer, 1799) – K14 (1 ♂); K16 (1 ♂).

**Bembidion (Ocyturanus) balcanicum* Apfelbeck, 1899 – K01 (1 ♀).

***Bembidion (Peryphanes) brunnicorne* Dejean, 1831 – K07 (1 ♀); K11 (1 ♂); K25 (1 ♀).

Bembidion (Peryphanes) dalmatinum dalmatinum Dejean, 1831 – K16 (2 ♂♂, 1 ♀); K20 (2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀); K24 (2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀).

Bembidion (Peryphanes) deletum deletum Audinet-Serville, 1821 – K04 (1 ♂, 3 ♀♀); K07 (1 ♂, 3 ♀♀).

Bembidion (Peryphus) subcostatum vau Netolitzky, 1913 – K07 (1 ♂, 2 ♀♀); K11 (1 ♀); K12 (1 ♂, 1 ♀).

**Calathus (Calathus) distinguendus* Chaudoir, 1846 – K05 (1 ♀); K07 (2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀); K13 (2 ♂♂); K15 (1 ♀); K29 (1 ♀).

Calathus (Calathus) fuscipes (Goeze, 1777) – K12 (1 ♂).

Calathus (Neocalathus) albanicus Apfelbeck, 1906 – K01 (2 ♀♀).

Calathus (Neocalathus) melanocephalus melanocephalus (Linnaeus, 1758) – K03 (1 ♂); K07 (1 ♂); K29 (1 ♂).

Calathus (Neocalathus) metallicus metallicus Dejean, 1828 – K10 (1 ♀).

***Carabus (Archicarabus) montivagus vellepiticus* Hampe, 1850 – K01 (1 ♂); K02 (1 ♂, 1 ♀); K03 (1 ♀); K04 (1 ♂).

Carabus (Chaetocarabus) intricatus intricatus Linnaeus, 1760 – K05 (1 ex); K21 (2 ex); K27 (1 ex); K28 (1 ex).

***Carabus (Megodontus) caelatus caelatus* Fabricius, 1801 – K02 (1 ♂).

Carabus (Megodontus) violaceus azureus Dejean, 1826 – K03 (1 ♀); K05 (1 ♀); K26 (1 ex).

Carabus (Pachystus) hortensis hortensis Linnaeus, 1758 – K02 (1 ex); K05 (17 ex); K21 (6 ex).

Carabus (Procrustes) coriaceus hopffgarteni Kraatz, 1877 – K21 (1 ex); K26 (1 ex); K27 (2 ex).

Chlaenius (Chlaeniellus) vestitus (Paykull, 1790) – K16 (1 ♀).

Cymindis (Cymindis) humeralis (Geoffroy, 1785) – K01 (2 ♂♂); K03 (10 ex).

***Cymindis (Cymindis) scapularis* Schaum, 1857 – K15 (1 ♂).

Harpalus (Cryptophonus) tenebrosus Dejean, 1829 – K01 (1 ♂); K21 (1 ♂).

Harpalus (Harpalus) affinis (Schrank, 1781) – K07 (3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀); K13 (2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀).

Harpalus (Harpalus) atratus Latreille, 1804 – K20 (1 ♂, 1 ♀).

Harpalus (Harpalus) attenuatus Stephens, 1828 – K17 (1 ♂).

- **Harpalus (Harpalus) flavicornis flavicornis** Dejean, 1829 – K14 (1 ♀).
Harpalus (Harpalus) rubripes (Duftschmid, 1812) – K11 (1 ♂); K14 (3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀); K22 (1 ♀).
Harpalus (Harpalus) smaragdinus (Duftschmid, 1812) – K14 (1 ♀).
****Harpalus (Harpalus) solitaris** Dejean, 1829 – K10 (1 ♀).
****Harpalus (Harpalus) tardus** (Panzer, 1796) – K20 (1 ♀).
Harpalus (Pseudoophonus) rufipes (De Geer, 1774) – K19 (1 ♂, 1 ♀).
****Leistus (Leistus) ferrugineus** (Linnaeus, 1758) – K07 (1 ♂).
Leistus (Pogonophorus) magnicollis Motschulsky, 1866 – K09 (1 ♂, 1 ♀); K29 (1 ♀).
****Leistus (Pogonophorus) parvicollis** Chaudoir, 1869 – K07 (1 ♀).
****Leistus (Pogonophorus) rufomarginatus** (Duftschmid, 1812) – K14 (1 ♂).
****Licinus (Licinus) depressus** (Paykull, 1790) – K07 (1 ♂).
****Limodromus assimilis** (Paykull, 1790) – K02 (1 ♀).
Molops (Molops) piceus balcanicus Mlynář, 1977 – K29 (1 ♂).
Molops (Molops) simplex simplex Chaudoir, 1868 – K03 (1 ♀); K10 (1 ♀).
Molops (Stenochoromus) montenegrinus (s.l.) L. Miller, 1866 – K10 (1 ♀).
Myas (Myas) chalybaeus Palliardi, 1825 – K21 (17 ex); K27 (2 ex).
Nebria (Nebria) brevicollis (Fabricius, 1792) – K02 (1 ♂); K16 (1 ♂).
****Ophonus (Metoponus) schaubergerianus** (Puel, 1937) – K17 (1 ♂).
****Ophonus (Metoponus) veluchianus** (J. Müller, 1931) – K13 (1 ♂); K18 (2 ♂♂).
****Platyderus (Platyderus) rufus rufus** Duftschmid, 1812 – K03 (1 ♂).
Platynus scrobiculatus serbicus Csiki, 1904 – K02 (10 ex); K05 (1 ♀); K07 (1 ♂); K09 (1 ♂, 1 ♀); K11 (1 ♂, 2 ♀♀).
Pterostichus (Bothriopterus) oblongopunctatus (s.l.) (Fabricius, 1787) – K08 (1 ♂).
Pterostichus (Cheporus) burmeisteri burmeisteri Heer, 1838 – K05 (3 ex).
Pterostichus (Feronidius) melas depressus Dejean, 1828 – K02 (1 ♂).
****Pterostichus (Platysma) niger niger** (Schaller, 1783) – K06 (1 ♂); K07 (1 ♀).
Pterostichus (Pterostichus) bruckii Schaum, 1859 – K05 (1 ♀); K09 (3 ♀♀).
****Synuchus (Synuchus) vivalis vivalis** Illiger, 1798 – K04 (1 ♀).
****Stomis pumicatus pumicatus** Panzer, 1796 – K03 (1 ♂).
****Tachyura (Tachyura) diabrachys** (Kolenati, 1845) – K12 (1 ♂); K16 (1 ♂).
Trechus (Balcanotrechus) priapus priapus K. Daniel, 1902 – K11 (1 ♂, 1 ♀).
Trechus (Calotrechus) obtusus obtusus Erichson, 1837 – K07 (2 ♀♀).
Trechus (Latotrechus) irenis Csiki, 1912 – K11 (1 ♂).
Trechus (Latotrechus) subnotatus ljubetensis Apfelbeck, 1908 – K02 (1 ♂).
****Trechus (Nigrinotrechus) kobingeri kobingeri** Apfelbeck, 1902 – K01 (2 ♀♀).
Trechus (Nigrinotrechus) nigrinus Putzeys, 1847 – K14 (1 ♂, 2 ♀♀); K16 (1 ♂); K17 (1 ♂).
Trechus (Trechus) quadristriatus (Schrank, 1781) – K14 (3 ♂♂); K23 (4 ♂♂, 1 ♀).
Zabrus (Pelor) albanicus albanicus Apfelbeck, 1904 – K01 (1 ♂).

Four genera (*Licinus*, *Limodromus*, *Stomis*, *Tachyura*) and 21 species are recorded for the first time for the fauna of Kosovo. In addition, five species (*Amara apricaria*, *Bembidion balcanicum*, *Calathus distinguendus*, *Synuchus vivalis*, *Trechus subnotatus ljubetensis*) and two genera (*Platyderus*, *Synuchus*) are first noted for Kosovo with first detailed records.
Some other taxa (31 species) are considered second detailed records for Kosovo. Most of them save four (*Aptinus merditanus*, cfr. Hůrka, 1988; *Chlaenius vestitus*, cfr. Apfelbeck, 1904; *Cymindis humeralis* and *Myas chalybaeus*, cfr. Guéorguiev, 2011) have been reported first time for Kosovo by Csiki (1940): *Bembidion dalmatinum dalmatinum*, *B. decorum decorum*, *B. deletum deletum*, *B. geniculatum geniculatum*, *B. lampros*, *B. subcostatum vau*, *B. tibiale*, *Calathus albanicus*, *C. bosnicus*, *C. metallicus metallicus*, *Carabus violaceus azureus*, *Harpalus affinis*, *H. rufipes*, *H. smaragdinus*, *H. tenebrosus*, *Molops piceus balcanicus*, *Nebria brevicollis*, *Platynus scrobiculatus serbicus*, *Pterostichus bruckii*, *Pt. burmeisteri burmeisteri*, *Pt. melas depressus*, *Pt.*

oblongopunctatus, *Trechus irenis*, *Tr. nigrinus*, *Tr. obtusus obtusus*, *Tr. priapus priapus*, *Tr. quadristriatus*.

Comments on some taxa representing first detailed findings for Kosovo are given in the following paragraphs.

Bembidion (Ocyturanus) balcanicus is distributed on the Balkan Peninsula, Italy and Romania (Marggi et al. 2017). The last source contains the only indication for Kosovo that we know, but it lacks precise locality and other particular data. Therefore, the finding at Piribeg is the first detailed record for the region. The species is rare and ordinary found above 1500 m a.s.l. (Guéorguiev & Guéorguiev 1995; Guéorguiev 1998).

In the Balkan Peninsula, *Platyderus (Platyderus) rufus rufus* was so far known from Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, North Macedonia and Serbia (Apfelbeck, 1904; Guéorguiev & Guéorguiev, 1995; Guéorguiev, 2007; Hristovski & Guéorguiev, 2015). Here the species is noted for the first time from Kosovo. Its congener, *P. dalmatinus dalmatinus* L. Miller, 1881 has been cited for Kosovo without precise locality and particularised data (Hovorka, 2017a), so that the latter needs further confirmation. *Platyderus dalmatinus* (s.l.) is a West Balkan endemic species that most probably does not dwell the Apennines (Guéorguiev, 2009).

Calathus (Calathus) distinguendus is a common species that can be distinguished from its close congener *C. fuscipes*, with which it is often mixed, by the short metepisterna, not longer than wide (Arndt, 2011). The former species predominates in the mountains whereas the latter prefers more xeric places of lower altitudes. Recently, *C. distinguendus* was indicated for Kosovo without precise locality and particularised data (Hovorka, 2017b). Due to our work the species is here identified from four localities so its presence in the region is confirmed.

Trechus subnotatus ljubotensis has been taxonomically treated by Jeannel (1927). The author cited it from “Serbie, Macédoine : mont Ljubeten, dans la chaîne du Schâr Dagh...Ce *Trechus* se prend suelement au-dessus de 1.500 m. d’altitude” [Serbia, Macedonia: Mount Ljubeten, in the Schar Dagh Range... This *Trechus* species is only taken above 1500 m altitude]. This geographic indication encloses the whole upper part of the Šar Planina Mountains today situated in the border territories of Albania, Kosovo and North Macedonia. Notwithstanding, no precise locality for this subspecies from Kosovo was known until now (see also Curcic et al., 2007). Accordingly, the locality near

Prevalac represents first detailed datum for this local endemic from Kosovo.

Synuchus vivalis and *Amara apricaria* are further two species that have been cited without precise localities for Kosovo (Hovorka, 2017c; Hieke, 2017). It seem that all such “first” indications for Kosovo in the updated issue of the Palaearctic catalogue of the ground beetles (Löbl & Löbl 2017) reflect real material in collections which in view of the of the specificities of the catalogue could not been “properly” cited. The last two aforementioned taxa are as well confirmed for the fauna of the region.

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